

School Atmosphere and Teachers' Performance in Public Elementary Schools' in Bambang I District

¹Jake Bryant M. Esteves^{ID}, ²Generose S. Ognayon^{ID}

¹Department of Education, ^{1,2}Ifugao State University

¹bryantjake806@gmail.com, ²gsognayon@gmail.com

Article Details:

Received: 8 April 2026

Revised: 15 March 2026

Accepted: 20 April 2026

Published: 30 April 2026

Corresponding Email:

bryantjake806@gmail.com

Recommended Citation:

Esteves, J.B., Ognayon, G.S., (2026). School Atmosphere and Teachers' Performance in Public Elementary Schools' in Bambang I District. The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research. 1 (4), 804-818.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20025628>

Index Terms:

faculty relations, leadership and decision-making, learning and assessments, organizational climate, school atmosphere, teachers' performance

Abstract. This study examined the relationship between school atmosphere and teachers' performance in public elementary schools in Bambang I District, Division of Nueva Vizcaya, during the Academic Year 2025–2026. Grounded in Organizational Climate Theory, the research employed a quantitative descriptive-comparative and correlational design. Data were gathered using an adapted School Climate Assessment Instrument (SCAI). The study assessed eight dimensions of school atmosphere: physical appearance, faculty relations, leadership and decision-making, discipline environment, community relations, attitude and culture, learning and assessments, and student interactions. The results of the study indicates that the general school atmosphere in Bambang I District had a “high” level of rating, signifying a positive and good school atmosphere. In terms of the dimension, leadership and decision-making as well as faculty relationships were given the highest rating among the eight dimensions, suggesting the presence of excellent management and faculty cooperation. Moreover, the teachers' performance also had an “outstanding” rating level, which signifies good teachers' performance. Through statistical analysis, it can be concluded that there exists a positive correlation between school atmosphere and teachers' performance. In conclusion, it can be said that school atmosphere plays a significant role in the performance of teachers. Positive leadership, effective collaboration, and conducive school atmosphere help improve teachers' performance.

Introduction

Education is acknowledged all over the world as the foundation of a nation's development. It determines the intellectual, moral, and social profile of a society by developing the youth who are the hope to make significant contributions to society. Our country, the Department of Education (DepEd) remains committed on improving the quality of learning and teaching through reforms, programs, and policies that ensure a healthy school climate. One of the most important determinants of education quality is the school climate a complex construct that involves the social, affective, and organizational environments within the school that determine how school administrators, teachers, parents and learners interact and work together.

A school atmosphere is an aggregation of shared perceptions, attitudes, and relationships between administrators, teachers, parents and learners. It is a major determining factor in the effectiveness of the school, influencing the daily existence of those who occupy it. A good school atmosphere promotes collaboration, trust, respect for one another, and shared commitment to academic excellence. In contrast, a bad environment of poor leadership, absence of administrative support, tense relationships, and poor facilities may promote demotivation, tension, and burnout among staff, ultimately affecting pupil outcomes.

The Bambang I District within the Division of Nueva Vizcaya is a vibrant educational scene consisting of elementary and secondary schools with diverse sizes, resources, and administrative procedures. Located in a largely rural environment, the schools in the district are confronted with unique challenges like limited infrastructure, geographical limitations, and disparities in resources. Despite all these challenges, most teachers within the district still insist on showing commitment and excellence in teaching. Due to these challenges, there is a need to examine how the school atmosphere

influences teachers' performance in Bambang I District. By studying systematically, the link between these two variables, the researcher aims to establish empirical findings that can guide local education policies and school development plans. School atmosphere is a construct that has multiple interdependent aspects. It encompasses Physical Appearance, Faculty Relations, Leadership/ Decision Making, Discipline Environment, Community Relations, Attitude and Culture, Learning and Assessments, Student Interactions Leadership is frequently cited as the single most influential determinant of school atmosphere because principals establish the tone for communication, discipline, and collaboration. Teachers who view their principals as supportive and fair are more likely to report increased job satisfaction and greater commitment to the school's goals. Strong and collaborative school leadership has been linked to improved student achievement and organizational effectiveness. In the study of Leithwood, K., et al (2020) they noted that effective school leadership involves setting direction, developing people, and creating a conducive learning environment. Similarly, Harris, A. (2020) highlighted in his study the importance of distributed leadership in promoting collective responsibility among staff, while Hallinger, P. (2019) said on his study that leadership for learning is a central to student good outcomes. This supports the claim with the study of Deal, T. E., and Peterson, K. D. (2016) they have discussed that the role of school culture in shaping norms and expectations, noting that leaders who actively shape a positive culture can enhance teacher commitment and student success.

Collegiality, or the nature of relationships among instructors, is also important. Teamwork and respect for one another foster innovation and help prevent professional isolation. In addition, a safe, clean, and well-equipped physical environment leads to pride and comfort in the workplace. Finally, professional development opportunities keep instructors motivated and supplied with current pedagogical skill. Peer relationships play a pivotal role in academic motivation and psychosocial development. According to Bagwell, C. L., & Schmidt, M. E. (2017) they emphasized that friendships in childhood and adolescence provide emotional support, enhance social skills, and reduce experiences of victimization. Similarly with the study of Wentzel, K. R. (2020) emphasized that positive peer interactions foster motivation and contribute to higher academic performance. In addition, the study of Graham, S. (2018) also suggested that reducing peer victimization through structured programs enhances both student well-being and school engagement. Moreover, parental and community engagement has been shown to improve student outcomes across multiple domains. This claim is supported by the study of Epstein, J.L. (2019) and Mapp, K.L. (2017) they both highlighted the importance of partnerships between schools, families, and communities to support student learning and development. Similarly, in the study of Henderson, A. T., and Mapp, K. L. (2016) they found that active participation of family can increase academic achievement and reduces dropout rates. Sheldon, S. B. and Epstein, J. L. (2019) also stressed that the role of school programs in creating structured opportunities is for family engagement.

The researcher has lit its curiosity that attempts in investigating school atmosphere and teacher performance in Bambang I District in the academic year 2025–2026. It will consider how dimensions of Physical Appearance, Faculty Relations, Leadership/ Decision-Making, Discipline Environment, Community Relations, Attitude and Culture, Learning and Assessments, Student Interactions The research findings will contribute to the expanding literature on educational management and yield practical insights for the district and school administrators.

Additionally, the findings of this study can help DepEd Nueva Vizcaya to discover best practices and improve areas in establishing a more positive and more productive learning environment. Through the knowledge of the interaction between school atmosphere and teacher performance, administrators are able to craft appropriate interventions like leadership training, team-building activities, or wellness programs that enhance teacher satisfaction and proficiency.

The research emphasizes the concept that the school atmosphere is not just a situational circumstance but a strategic factor that produces the overall quality of education. Educators prosper in an atmosphere where they feel encouraged, motivated, and part of a working team. Developing this kind of atmosphere calls for conscious leadership, regular communication, and collective vision. As Bambang I District moves towards educational greatness, identifying and developing the elements that support a good school atmosphere becomes not only desirable but indispensable.

Finally, the researcher wanted to conduct this study to determine the relationship of the school atmosphere on teachers' performance in Bambang I District during the academic year 2025-2026 to provides insights for improving the school atmosphere to support teachers' effectiveness, encourages self-assessment and promotes collaboration toward a positive work environment and will serve as a reference for further studies on school management and teacher performance.

Theoretical and conceptual framework

School atmosphere plays a vital role in running an organization especially that a leader is dealing with a diverse subordinate. So, a leader should be flexible and effective by having a strong, appropriate, and an acceptable leadership styles. A leader should be flexible because in each situation he will be facing different kinds of problems and challenges

while running the organization. In addition, collegiality, professional development of teachers is a must in the field because it will affect the teachers' performance especially in delivering a quality basic education to the learners.

This study will focus on the chosen respondents in Bambang I District specifically the teachers of the four (4) big schools of the said district. It will focus on the school atmosphere as the independent variable with eight (8) dimensions: Physical Appearance, Faculty Relations, Leadership/ Decision Making, Discipline Environment, Community Relations, Attitude and Culture, Learning and Assessments, Student Interactions.

School leadership and administration refer to the quality and effectiveness in guiding, supporting, and managing the school community. It includes the ability of school leaders to provide clear direction, foster a shared vision, support teachers and staff, and ensure the smooth operation of school programs and policies. Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping the school's culture. Effective administrators create environments where teachers feel trusted and supported. Conversely, poor leadership can lead to dissatisfaction, high turnover, and reduced performance.

This study is based on Organizational Climate Theory developed by Litwin, G. H., and Stringer, R. A. (1968) their theory proposes that the internal environment in any organization plays a significant role in determining the behavior, motivation, and performance of organizational members. The organizational climate involves the perceptions of individuals about leadership styles, relationships among employees, communication styles, policies, and the working conditions in an organization. The internal environment affects the thoughts, emotions, and performance of individuals.

Schools can be viewed as formal organizations, where teachers work under an established structure characterized by leadership styles, relationships among colleagues, physical environment, and organizational culture. Hence, organizational climate is evident in the school environment as school atmosphere or climate, which becomes one of the key determinants of effective teaching and professional behaviors of teachers.

The theory of school climate is further supported by School Climate Organizational Theory proposed by Hoy, W. K. and Miskel, C. G. (2013). The theory asserts that the internal features of the school such as leadership behavior, relationships between teachers, and organizational processes generate a unique school climate, which affects the behavior and performance of teachers in the school environment.

This theoretical framework is used in this current research work as part of defining school atmosphere as the organizational climate influencing teacher performance. This research study examines school atmosphere as the independent variable and includes the following aspects: physical appearance, faculty relations, leadership and decision making, discipline environment, community relations, attitude and culture, learning and assessment, and student interactions.

Leadership and decision-making relate to how school leaders provide leadership and direction. To support my claim, in the study of Castillo (2017) a local setting; found that Filipino teachers perceive supportive principals as key to maintaining high morale and reducing workplace stress. Leadership that encourages open communication, participative decision-making, and recognition of achievements significantly improves teachers' job satisfaction. Similarly to the study of De Guzman, R. S. C., et al (2019) in their study it explored the influence of school climate on teachers' job satisfaction in the University of the Philippines and it turns out that administrative support and opportunities for professional growth were key factors affecting performance and retention. Lastly, in the study of Bautista, M.C and Ramos, L.G (2020) studied high school teachers in Central Luzon and found that participative leadership and a positive emotional climate led to better RPMS ratings and stronger work commitment.

Faculty relations relate to how much teachers interact and cooperate in their professional capacity at schools. According to Fullan, M. (2016), in his study he reveals that schools that promote teamwork and collaboration achieve higher innovation and adaptability. When teachers share ideas, mentor each other, and work collectively toward common goals, they experience professional growth and increased job satisfaction. Furthermore, the study of Calaguas, G. (2013) in the Philippines showed that collegiality contributes significantly to teachers' sense of belonging and organizational commitment. Teachers in collegial environments tend to stay longer in the profession and report greater enthusiasm for teaching. According to the study of Dela Cruz, R. (2020) examined the correlation between school climate and teacher performance in the Division of Bulacan. The study found a significant positive relationship, particularly between leadership support and instructional performance. Likewise, in the studies of Quijano, J. and Arrieta, J. (2021) they have observed that collegial environments lead to higher teacher engagement and lower absenteeism in rural schools. Lastly, in the study of Magno, R. B. (2018) it investigated public elementary schools in Cagayan Valley and found that leadership and collegiality were the strongest predictors of teacher effectiveness. Teachers who felt valued by their principals and colleagues exhibited higher engagement and instructional quality.

Discipline environment and attitude and culture pertain to the values and behavioral expectations that exist in the social climate of schools. Physical appearance involves the physical state of school premises. These dimensions cover the safety, comfort, and overall well-being of all individuals within the school premises. It includes the adequacy of school facilities and resources, physical conditions such as cleanliness and maintenance, as well as the presence of an emotionally supportive and secure atmosphere conducive to learning and teaching. In addition, it includes classroom conditions, facilities, and resources directly affects teachers' comfort and efficiency. Similarly, the psychological environment, which involves safety, respect, and emotional support, determines how teachers perceive their work setting. DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019, stresses that a safe, inclusive, and supportive environment enhances both student learning and teacher well-being. Schools that uphold fairness, discipline, and respect foster positive interactions that translate to improved work outcomes. Community relations pertain to the degree to which communities engage in school affairs. Learning and assessment and student interactions involve the educational activities in schools.

In contrast, teachers' performance, which is the dependent variable, entails the degree to which the teachers effectively play their role as professionals. These include instructional effectiveness, classroom management skills, work commitment, and involvement in professional activities. The teachers' performance is considered an effect resulting from a combination of individuals' competencies and the prevailing environment at the school. In the study of Danielson, C. (2013), defines that the effective teaching as the ability to create engaging learning experiences, manage classroom dynamics, and assess students' progress fairly. Similarly, the DepEd RPMS evaluates teachers based on Key Result Areas (KRAs): content knowledge, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and community linkages. In addition, teacher performance is not static it is influenced by intrinsic motivation and extrinsic factors, such as leadership, workload, and working conditions.

Based on the theory of Organizational Climate, this research study is guided by the assumption that a good school environment improves the performance of teachers through increased motivation, satisfaction, and effectiveness. On the contrary, a bad organizational environment could reduce teachers' motivation and their capacity to be effective in performing their duties as teachers. Therefore, the conceptual framework of the research study suggests that there is a significant relationship between school atmosphere and teachers' performance.

The research paradigm below depicts how a positive school environment is the input while teachers' performance is the output. Additionally, analyzing the relationship between the two forms the basis for the proposed interventions.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm of the Study

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher employed quantitative research approach in the conduct of the study. Specifically, it utilized descriptive comparative and correlational design as it describes the school atmosphere and teachers' performance. It also compared the assessment of respondents on school atmosphere. Finally, the relationship between the school atmosphere and teachers' performance was assessed.

The study utilized a questionnaire to determine the school atmosphere of Bambang I District and its influence to teachers' performance. The researcher used numerical values to identify the school atmosphere of the said schools and its correlation to teachers' performance. The use of numerical values would make this study as quantitative research.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya. Bambang has twenty-five barangays and it is divided into two (2) districts. The researcher chose Bambang I to study about the school atmosphere of the four (4) big schools of the said district; specifically, Bambang Central School Integrated SPED Center, Sto. Domingo Integrated School, Indiana Integrated School and Bambang West Elementary School and its relationship on teachers' performance.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are the elementary teachers, junior high school teachers, administrative officers and school administrations at Bambang I District in Bambang; Nueva Vizcaya and parents of pupils enrolled in the different schools of the district. The researcher used a quota sampling with 107 teachers and 30 parents from each of the school in Bambang I District as the sample. The distribution of respondents is shown in Table 1.

Name Of School	Teachers in Elem.	Teachers in Junior High School (JHS)	School Administrator (Principal, & TIC)	Administrative Officers (AO)	PTA-Officers	TOTAL
Bambang Central School Integrated SPED Center	35	2	1	5	8	51
Sto. Domingo Integrated School	14	13	1	2	8	38
Indiana Integrated School	14	7	1	1	7	30
Bambang West Elementary School	9	0	1	1	7	18
TOTAL	72	22	4	9	30	137

Research Instrument

The researcher used the adopted School Climate Assessment Instrument (SCAI) Elementary level questionnaire to examine the school atmosphere. This questionnaire helped both the aspiring school administrators and the full-pledge administrators, teachers and future researchers to understand the school atmosphere of Bambang I District. Recent studies also used this instrument; in 2023, Simbre A. P. et al used this tool to assess students' perceptions of the school climate level. Same questionnaire is also used by Atolba, I. B. (2012) to assess the school atmosphere of public and private secondary schools in the Division of Ifugao.

The questionnaire provides eight (8) categories of what is the atmosphere of the school: Physical Appearance, Faculty Relations, Leadership/Decision-Making, Discipline Environment, Community Relations, Attitude and Culture, Learning Assessment and Student Interactions which determined by a participant's cumulative scores. The participant had to choose level one (1)-low, level two (2)-middle, level three (3)-high. The questionnaire explained by the researcher before giving it to the respondents, for them to avoid misconceptions while answering the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first asked permission to the Public School District Supervisor (PSDS) of Bambang I District through a request letter. Then, upon the approval of the request, the researcher asked permission once again to each school principals of Bambang I District to conduct the said study. Upon the approval of the request, the researcher has immediately floated the questionnaire in each school. After floating questionnaire, the researcher made two call backs to ensure that all respondents were able to answer the questionnaire. The gathered data was tabulated and summarized ready for data analysis.

Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical analysis was employed to answer the research question of the study.

To determine the school atmosphere of the four (4) schools of Bambang I District, weighted mean was employed. In order to determine the significant difference of the assessment of respondents in terms of school and type of respondent, F-test was utilized. To determine the correlation between school atmosphere and teachers' performance, Pearson product moment correlation was used in the study. The SPSS was employed to process the data.

Results and Discussion

This chapter will show the result of the study conducted to determine the school climate as perceived by the respondents in terms of the dimensions of physical appearance, faculty relations, leadership and decision-making, discipline environment, community relations, attitude and culture, learning and assessment, and student interactions. The gathered data was analyzed using the mean and interpreted according to the level of school climate observed in the school. Each dimension was presented to provide a deeper understanding of the result in relation to the literature.

School Atmosphere

Summary Of Findings of All the Aspect of School Atmosphere

Table 10 shows the summary of findings of all the aspects of school climate received high ratings, ranging from 2.73 to 2.86. This means that the school has a positive and supportive school climate in all critical areas, which include leadership, faculty relations, discipline, community relations, student relations, and learning processes. The consistency of high ratings in school climate indicates that the school has been able to create a balanced school climate, which supports teaching effectiveness and student development.

In particular, it is evident that the school has effective leadership and decision-making, which received the highest ratings. This means that the school has effective and participatory leadership. This is a critical aspect in school effectiveness. According to the study of Leithwood, K., et.al, (2020) they revealed that school leadership has a great impact on school effectiveness, teacher motivation, and student performance, especially when it involves decision-making and cooperation among teachers.

On the other hand, attitude and culture, while still rated high, had the lowest mean value in all the dimensions. This may imply that, while the school is successful in instilling a sense of belonging and positive values, there may be some areas, like respectful communication and student behavior, which may need improvement. School culture is a vital aspect in the creation of students' experiences and outcomes. Wang, M. and Degol, J.L. (2019) stressed the importance of students' perceptions of school culture and school climate in relation to their emotional well-being, engagement, and academic outcomes.

While the ratings in all the dimensions were high, this may imply that the school is a place where everyone works together in a collaborative, supportive, and inclusive manner. Such positive faculty relations and collaborative practices are important in enhancing the quality of instruction, as noted by Hammond, L.D., et al. (2020). In addition, positive discipline and teacher-student relationships are important in creating safe learning environments, which enhance student engagement, as noted by Gregory, A. et al. (2019). Moreover, positive community relations and parental involvement are important in enhancing student outcomes and school effectiveness, as noted by Epstein, J.L. (2018).

In addition to these findings, Cohen, J. et al. (2019) stated that a positive school climate, which refers to safety, relationships, teaching and learning, and institutional environment, plays a crucial role in enhancing student achievement, well-being, and success. Similarly, Hattie, J. (2018) found that factors such as collective teacher efficacy and relationships under the category of school climate-related factors were among the most influential factors in enhancing student learning.

The results have several important implications for educational management. Firstly, the high ratings in all dimensions show that the school has already established effective systems and practices that need to be maintained and further enhanced. Therefore, school management needs to sustain these systems and practices by building on what is already working well in the school.

Secondly, the high ratings in leadership and decision-making show that school management needs to continue with participatory and distributive leadership in education management. Therefore, school management needs to continue to involve teachers in the school's decision-making process.

Thirdly, the low rating in attitude and culture implies that school management needs to introduce more effective strategies to further enhance school values, particularly in promoting positive student behavior. Therefore, school management needs to further develop values education programs.

Lastly, the positive school climate presents an opportunity for school management to introduce more sophisticated and innovative strategies in education management to further enhance student outcomes. Therefore, school management needs to take advantage of the positive school climate to introduce more sophisticated and innovative strategies in education management.

Finally, school management needs to institutionalize monitoring and evaluation of school climate to ensure data-driven decisions in education management. In conclusion, based on the summary of results, it is clear that there is a healthy and supportive school climate that encourages academic excellence and holistic development. Effective education management is very important in maintaining these conditions while improving on the areas that need improvement to achieve growth and success.

Dimensions	Mean	Level
Physical Appearance	2.77	High
Faculty Relations	2.83	High
Leadership/Decisions	2.86	High
Discipline Environment	2.84	High
Community Relations	2.84	High
Attitude and Culture	2.73	High
Learning/Assessment	2.83	High
Student Interactions	2.83	High

Difference in the Assessment of School Climate when Grouped by School

Table 11 presents the analysis of variance (ANOVA) results examining whether significant differences exist in the assessment of school climate when respondents are grouped according to school. The results showed that no significant differences exist in the dimensions of physical appearance, faculty attitude, assessment practices, and student-related aspects of the school climate. However, significant differences exist in the dimensions of leadership, discipline, and community, which are important components of the school climate.

The results showing no significant difference exist in the dimensions of physical appearance, faculty attitude, assessment practices, and student-related aspects of the school climate indicate that these dimensions are perceived uniformly across the schools. The uniformity may be attributed to the fact that these dimensions are important components of the educational system and are uniformly addressed through the educational policies and guidelines that are followed by the schools in Bambang I District. The schools are required to follow a uniform educational policy, and the educational system is responsible for developing guidelines for teaching and learning that are uniformly followed across the schools. The schools are also required to adhere to a uniform code of conduct and guidelines for the administration and supervision of the educational system. The schools are also required to ensure that the educational policies and guidelines are uniformly followed, and this may have resulted in the uniformity observed in the dimensions of physical appearance, faculty attitude, assessment practices, and student-related aspects of the school climate.

Domain	School	Mean	Level	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Physical Appearance	A	2.80	High	0.980	0.404	No Significant Difference
	B	2.85	High			
	C	2.73	High			
	D	2.75	High			
Faculty Relations	A	2.86	High	1.610	0.190	No Significant Difference
	B	2.89	High			
	C	2.77	High			
Leadership/ Decision Making	D	2.83	High	3.849	0.011	Significant Difference
	A	2.93 ^a	High			
	B	2.97 ^a	High			
	C	2.79 ^b	High			
	D	2.85 ^b	High	2.550	0.048	Significant Difference
	A	2.81 ^b	High			
	B	2.94 ^a	High			

Discipline Environment	C	2.79 ^b	High	4.883	0.003	Significant Difference
	D	2.91 ^a	High			
	A	2.94 ^a	High			
Community Relations	B	2.96 ^a	High	0.845	0.472	No Significant Difference
	C	2.75 ^b	High			
	D	2.78 ^b	High			
Attitude and Culture	A	2.77	High	1.098	0.352	No Significant Difference
	B	2.64	High			
	C	2.71	High			
Learning and Assessment	D	2.76	High	0.714	0.545	No Significant Difference
	A	2.87	High			
	B	2.77	High			
Student Interactions	C	2.80	High			
	D	2.86	High			
	A	2.87	High			
	B	2.78	High			
	C	2.83	High			
	D	2.81	High			

Mean with the same letter are not significantly different

Table 11. Assessment of School Climate when Grouped by School

Type Of Respondent

Table 12 presents the results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the assessment of school climate when respondents are grouped according to type of respondent. From the findings, it was revealed that no significant difference exists in the ratings on all aspects of school climate. This implies that the respondents, regardless of the category to which they belong, have similar perceptions about the school climate. The lack of significant difference implies that the respondents, regardless of the category to which they belong, have similar perceptions about the school climate. This implies that the different categories of people have similar experiences about the school climate. This is an indication that the different stakeholders have had similar experiences about the school climate. This is an indication that the school policies and practices are being implemented in an identical manner to all the members of the school community.

The similarity in perceptions about the school climate among the respondents, regardless of the category to which they belong, may be attributed to the collective nature of the school experience. The collective nature of the school experience implies that the school climate is affected in an identical manner to all the members of the school community. The collective nature of the school experience implies that the school policies and practices are being implemented in an identical manner to all the members of the school community.

Another possible reason for the similarities in the ratings is the presence of a common organizational structure and communication systems within the school setting. The emphasis on transparency, participatory decision-making, and communication among all stakeholders within the school setting minimizes the chances for different perceptions among all the different school groups. The presence of a common experience among all stakeholders within the school setting creates a collective perception of the school climate. This is why there was no statistically significant difference in the ratings of all the different respondents.

The findings of this study align with previous findings regarding the importance of realizing that school climate is a collective experience for all school stakeholders. Cohen, J. et al. (2019) assert that school climate is described as a collective perception of norms, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching mechanisms, and structural aspects within the school setting. These aspects affect all school stakeholders. It is thus possible for all school stakeholders to have similar perceptions regarding all aspects of the school setting. Thapa et al. (2018) assert that when school policies and practices are implemented in a consistent manner, it is possible for all stakeholders within the school setting to have similar perceptions regarding safety, relationships, teaching mechanisms, and support within the school setting. There was no statistically significant difference in the findings of this study. These findings thus support literature findings regarding school climate. Literature findings assert that a stable school setting creates a collective perception among all stakeholders within the school setting.

From the perspective of educational management, the lack of significant difference among the respondents also implies that the policies and management styles are being implemented well. This is because the school environment is being

viewed almost in the same manner by the respondents. This implies that the administration of the school is effectively communicating to the respondents. Moreover, the findings also highlight the need to promote inclusive leadership and participatory governance in schools. This is because, when the administration involves different stakeholders in the decision-making process, it is likely to promote mutual understanding and perception of the school environment. Therefore, educational management is advised to continue promoting inclusive leadership and participatory governance.

In addition, the findings also highlight the need to promote a shared perception of the school environment among different respondent groups. This is important in promoting and sustaining a positive school culture. Therefore, educational management is advised to continue monitoring the school climate. This will ensure that the emerging issues are addressed promptly. Moreover, the positive aspects of the school climate are maintained.

In general, the results show that the various types of respondents have a similar perception of the school climate in all the dimensions, which indicates that the school environment is perceived in the same way by all the members of the school community, implying the existence of stable organizational practices and effective school management.

Domain	Type of Respondent	Mean	Level	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Physical Appearance	Teaching	2.74	High	1.621	0.202	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.84	High			
	Admin	2.91	High			
Faculty Relations	Teaching	2.81	High	1.288	0.279	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.87	High			
	Admin	2.95	High			
Leadership/Decision Making	Teaching	2.85	High	0.707	0.495	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.89	High			
	Admin	2.98	High			
Discipline Environment	Teaching	2.83	High	0.134	0.875	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.86	High			
	Admin	2.88	High			
Community Relations	Teaching	2.82	High	1.422	0.245	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.89	High			
	Admin	3.00	High			
Attitude and Culture	Teaching	2.73	High	1.445	0.240	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.70	High			
	Admin	2.98	High			
Learning and Assessment	Teaching	2.85	High	2.392	0.095	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.75	High			
	Admin	2.93	High			
Student Interactions	Teaching	2.81	High	1.590	0.208	No Significant Difference
	Parents	2.87	High			
	Admin	2.97	High			

Table 12. Assessment of School Climate when Grouped by the Type of Respondents

Teachers' Performance

The results show that all the schools have achieved an "Outstanding" level of performance, and the range of the mean score is narrow, falling between 4.58 and 4.69, with an overall mean score of 4.64. This shows that the students are achieving highly and that there is consistency in the application of educational practice.

This is also confirmed by various studies carried out in educational research. For example, Leithwood, K. (2020) noted that good and consistent leadership in schools is a major factor that contributes to improved performance. Schools that exhibit high levels of leadership and a shared vision are able to sustain high levels of performance. Another example is that of Timperley, H. (2019), who noted that continuous professional learning among the teaching staff contributes to improved quality, which directly influences the overall performance of the school.

Furthermore, according to the research done by Hattie, J. (Visible Learning research), collective teacher efficacy is one of the most important factors to ensure that students attain high performance levels. The consistent high ratings for all schools may also be an indication that there is a high level of collaboration and a common goal to ensure that students succeed.

Additionally, Darling-Hammond, L., (2021) observed that schools that are well-supported and have the right systems, resources, and teacher development programs are likely to attain and sustain high performance levels.

The low variations observed among the means for all the schools may also be an indication that, according to Hargreaves, A. (2018), systems that promote professional collaboration and coherence among schools are likely to reduce performance gaps and ensure that all students are successful.

The findings highlight several implications for educational management. First, the outstanding performance is an indication that the school heads and administrators should continue to promote the implementation and sustenance of the effective leadership strategies.

Second, the findings are an indication that the value and importance of professional collaboration and learning communities cannot be overstated. The educational managers should promote the formation of Professional Learning Community (PLC's) where teachers can engage in the sharing of professional best practices, especially from slightly better-performing schools such as School B and School C.

Third, the data indicate that the educational managers should consider the need to have continuous monitoring and quality assurance mechanisms in place. The outstanding performance is an indication that, despite the high performance, evaluation mechanisms should be put in place to ensure that the high standard is maintained and that the performance does not drop to an average level.

Fourth, the slight differences in the scores are an indication that the educational managers can engage in the benchmarking and replication of the best practices from the top-performing schools, especially School B and School C, to enhance excellence in the system as a whole.

Finally, the outstanding performance is an indication that the educational managers should consider the need to have sustainable resource management and support mechanisms in place. The outstanding performance requires the school heads and administrators to invest in the teachers and the school environment.

In essence, the data reveal an educational system that is extremely effective and well-managed. The data, as supported by the literature, reveal the importance of leadership, teacher collaboration, and system coherence as determinants of outstanding school success. Educational managers must now focus on not only maintaining these strengths but also innovating to ensure excellence in the long term.

School	Mean	Performance
A	4.58	Outstanding
B	4.69	Outstanding
C	4.68	Outstanding
D	4.59	Outstanding
Over-all	4.64	Outstanding

Table 13. Summary of Teachers' Performance of Bambang I District

Relationship Between the School Atmosphere and Teachers' Performance

Table 14 presents the results of the correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship between school climate and teachers' performance in Bambang I District. The findings indicate the existence of a significant but low relationship between the performance of the teachers and various aspects of the school's climate, which include physical appearance, leadership, discipline, community, attitude, and assessment. On the other hand, the study established no significant relationship between the performance of the teachers and the aspects of the school's climate which include the faculty and the students.

Although the significant correlations established between the aspects of the school's climate and the performance of the teachers are low and insignificant, they indicate the possible influence of the various aspects of the school's climate on the performance of the teachers. Among the aspects of the school's climate which are significant and which could influence the performance of the teachers include the school's leadership, discipline, and community.

These aspects of the school's climate are deemed important organizational aspects of the school which can influence the effective performance of the functions of the teachers. The significant relationship established between the physical

appearance of the school and the performance of the teachers implies the possible influence of the organized school environment on the productivity and motivation of the teachers.

Therefore, the organized and neat school environment could motivate the teachers to perform more effectively and efficiently in the classroom and the school at large. Similarly, the significant relationship established between the assessment and attitude of the teachers and the school and the performance of the teachers implies the possible influence of the professional attitude of the teachers on the motivation and productivity of the teachers.

However, it is important to note that the strength of the correlation was weak, implying that although school climate has a bearing on teachers' performance, it is not a sole determinant. Teacher performance, among other factors, is affected by a combination of variables such as professional competence, motivation, and commitment, among others.

In contrast, findings revealed no correlation between teachers' performance and faculty and student school climate aspects. This implies that teachers' performance may not necessarily be affected by perceptions of teachers' relationships among faculty members and student school climate aspects, among others. This could be explained by the fact that teachers may be able to perform regardless of the nature of relationships among teachers and students, as they are likely to be guided by professional standards and expectations in terms of performance. Another possible explanation is that the respondents may already have stable professional relationships and manageable student interactions, resulting in minimal variation in these aspects across the schools. When there is little variability in the perceptions of faculty relationships and student climate, it becomes less likely for these variables to demonstrate significant statistical relationships with teachers' performance.

The findings of the current study are also supported by other studies that highlight the impact of school climate on teachers' effectiveness. Cohen et al. (2019) found that when the school climate is positive, it motivates teachers to work collaboratively and with greater commitment, thus leading to better performance. Another study done by Thapa et al. (2018) found that when the leadership is supportive, the school is well maintained, and the community is actively engaged, teachers are more likely to demonstrate good teaching practices.

On the other hand, the low correlation levels indicate that the impact of school climate on teachers' performance is probably indirect. This is also supported by the findings of Hoy and Miskel (2013), which indicate that the impact of school climate is on teachers' attitudes and satisfaction.

The implications of the results of the study are very important in the area of educational management, particularly in school leadership. First, the strong correlations obtained in the study between teachers' performance and certain aspects of school climate underscore the need to maintain a supportive school environment. Educational managers are advised to continue building leadership, discipline, and community aspects of school climate, as these are all beneficial in creating conditions for teachers to perform their duties effectively.

Second, school administrators are advised to focus on leadership strategies geared towards teacher support, professional collaboration, and communication, as these are effective in creating conditions for teachers to perform their duties effectively. Moreover, effective leadership can create conditions in which teachers will feel supported, which can positively affect teachers' performance.

Third, although the correlations are very weak, the results of the study suggest that enhancements in the physical environment, professional attitudes, and assessment can positively affect teachers' performance in the classroom. Educational managers are advised to continue building physical environment, professional attitudes, and assessment aspects of school climate, as these are all beneficial in creating conditions in which teachers can perform their duties effectively.

Finally, the lack of strong correlations between teachers' performance and the faculty and students' aspects of school climate suggest that teacher performance can be explained more by teachers' competencies and support systems than by school climate. Educational managers are advised to continue building teacher competencies, as these are very beneficial in creating conditions in which teachers can perform their duties effectively.

In conclusion, the study results indicate that, while the school climate contributes to the formation of teachers' professional experiences, the performance of teachers is affected by various organizational, professional, and personal factors. Strengthening the positive dimensions of school climate, along with teacher development programs, can lead to an improvement in school organizational effectiveness and teacher performance.

School	Coefficient	p-value	Remarks
Physical Appearance	0.251*	0.012	Significant
Faculty Relations	0.143	0.155	Not Significant
Leadership/ Decision Making	0.253*	0.011	Significant
Discipline Environment	0.211*	0.035	Significant
Community Relations	0.299**	0.002	Significant
Attitude and Culture	0.203*	0.042	Significant
Learning Assessment	0.228*	0.023	Significant
Student Interaction	0.192	0.055	Not Significant

Table 14. The Relationship Between the School Atmosphere and Teachers' Performance in Bambang I District

The findings of this study present significant implications for the Department of Education (DepEd) and school leaders in strengthening school climate as a foundation for improved educational outcomes.

1. Institutionalization of School Climate Programs

The consistently high ratings across all dimensions suggest that school climate initiatives are effective and should be sustained and institutionalized at the district and division levels. DepEd may strengthen policies that integrate school climate indicators into the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and School-Based Management (SBM) frameworks to ensure continuity and accountability.

2. Strengthening Participatory and Transformational Leadership

The high rating in leadership and decision-making highlights the importance of inclusive and participatory leadership practices. Educational management should prioritize leadership development programs that promote shared decision-making, teacher empowerment, and accountability. This reinforces DepEd's thrust toward transformational leadership in schools.

3. Enhancement of Teacher Professional Collaboration

Strong faculty relations indicate that collaborative practices contribute to school effectiveness. DepEd and school administrators should further strengthen Professional Learning Communities (PLCs), mentoring systems, and collaborative planning structures to sustain instructional improvement and teacher development.

4. Integration of Positive Discipline and Social-Emotional Learning (SEL)

The positive discipline environment underscores the effectiveness of respectful and consistent behavior management. However, concerns in student behavior, particularly in communication, suggest the need for DepEd to intensify the integration of SEL and values education into the curriculum and school programs. This will promote holistic learner development aligned with DepEd's child protection and inclusive education policies.

5. Strengthening School-Community Partnerships

The strong community relations emphasize the role of stakeholders in supporting school success. Educational management should maximize partnerships with parents, local government units (LGUs), and community organizations to support programs, resources, and student development initiatives. This aligns with DepEd's advocacy for shared governance in education.

6. Sustaining Learner-Centered Instruction and Assessment Practices

The high rating in learning and assessment reflects effective teaching strategies. DepEd should continue to support capacity-building programs focusing on formative assessment, differentiated instruction, and learner-centered pedagogies to further enhance student achievement.

7. Data-Driven Decision Making and Continuous Monitoring

The results highlight the importance of regularly assessing school climate. Educational leaders should adopt data-driven decision-making practices by integrating climate assessment tools into monitoring and evaluation systems. This ensures that interventions are responsive, targeted, and sustainable.

8. Focus on Culture-Building and Student Behavior Development

The relatively lower rating in attitude and culture indicates a need for stronger interventions in building a respectful and inclusive school culture. DepEd and school leaders should design culture-building programs that reinforce positive behavior, inclusivity, and mutual respect among learners.

The study affirms that a positive school climate is a critical driver of school effectiveness. For DepEd and educational managers, this underscores the need to move beyond compliance-based management toward strategic, culture-driven leadership that prioritizes relationships, collaboration, and holistic student development.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study has proven that the Bambang I District has managed to sustain a very positive and conducive school atmosphere based on all dimensions that were considered for this research work. The positive evaluation in physical appearance, faculty relations, leadership and decision-making, discipline atmosphere, community relations, learning and assessment, and student interactions shows that the schools have created an environment that facilitates effective teaching and learning processes. It means that the district has been successful in implementing systems and procedures that encourage order, cooperation, and academic pursuit. Nonetheless, the low rating in attitude and culture implies that although the overall climate has been very positive, there is still a need to enhance the development of good values, respectful communication, and positive relationships among the students.

Moreover, the results of the study showed that there was no significant difference between the evaluation of the school atmosphere based on school and respondent types. Therefore, it proves that the perception of school atmosphere has remained consistent in all schools within the district.

Furthermore, the study also establishes that teachers in Bambang I District exhibit a high degree of performance, from the overall rating that was recorded. It means that the teachers can perform their teaching functions effectively, use the appropriate methods, and help learners achieve better educational outcomes. The high level of performance could be because of a number of factors including the school environment, presence of professional working relations, and effective leadership within the district.

Also, the research established that there was a statistically significant relationship between school atmosphere and teacher performance. It means that the school environment plays a critical role in ensuring that teachers perform effectively and are productive. Some of the important aspects that play an enabling role include leadership, collegiality, safety, and order in schools.

Consequently, from the enumerated strength and weaknesses above, it can be concluded that proper interventions through administration are needed to be done to maintain and improve both the school atmosphere and performance of the teachers in the district. Although the current methods applied are already doing well, further strengthening of activities related to the attitude of students and culture are also necessary especially those aimed at instilling values like respect and positive discipline among others.

To conclude, Bambang I District clearly exhibits a positive and strong school atmosphere which enables excellent teacher performances. Nonetheless, continuing efforts must be made to deal with the areas that still require attention.

Acknowledgement

Completing my thesis for the Master of Arts in Education was truly a marathon. I recognized that I would not have been able to complete this journey without the aid and support of those who contributed invaluable assistance in various ways. To Dr. Generose S. Ognayon, my adviser and statistician who provided continuous support, patience, motivation, valuable comments, suggestions, and immense knowledge to ensure the research will be completed;

To Dr. Donato O. Abaya, the Chairperson of the Panel of Examiners, along with the members Dr. Michele Jaymalin-Dulay and Dr. Jeng M. Bolintao, who offered insightful feedback, encouragement, and dedicated their time to help me improve my work;

To Dr. Orlando E. Manuel, the Schools Division Superintendent of Nueva Vizcaya, motivated and inspired teachers, helping them to grow professionally;

To Mr. Arnel A. Panganiban, the Public Schools District Supervisor of Bambang I District, provided guidance and support throughout the conduct of her study;

To the School Heads of the various schools in Bambang I District aided me in retrieving the questionnaires from the respondents;

Additionally, the teachers who were the respondents of my study willingly and honestly answered the questionnaires, contributing to the success of my research;

Above all, to the omniscient God for all the bountiful blessings I received. TO GOD BE THE GLORY!

THE AUTHOR

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.